

IN-PLANE STRUCTURAL BEHAVIOR OF MASONRY PANELS STRENGTHENED WITH AN INNOVATIVE HEMP-BASED COMPOSITE SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Sustainability goals are essential driving principles for the development of innovative materials and technological solutions in the construction industry. Natural fibres represent an attractive alternative as reinforcing material in structural applications due to both good mechanical properties and the possibility to meet sustainability requirements. However, the use of these fibres as reinforcement in composite systems remains a challenge, especially for existing or historical masonry structures. The present work investigates the in-plane structural behaviour of masonry panels strengthened with an innovative reinforcing system based on the combination of a hemp fibre composite grid and two different mortars. The objective of the study is to assess the feasibility of using the proposed system for structural retrofit applications on existing masonry structures. The bi-directional composite grid is made of three twisted hemp yarns impregnated in a flexible epoxy resin. The tensile mechanical performance of the impregnated hemp yarns is optimized by controlling the content of resin within the composite and the twisting configuration of the hemp rope. The strengthening system is applied to the yellow tuff masonry panels by means of manual lay-up application. The results of the experimental campaign are presented in terms of compressive and shear strength, in-plane deformation and post peak softening regime of the reinforced panels. The results are finally compared with other commercial reinforcing solutions, in terms of failure mode and mechanical improvement, confirming the effectiveness of such a system as an innovative solution for external reinforcing of existing masonry structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the last decade, the structural rehabilitation of existing buildings has increasingly attracted the attention of scientific community. A significant focus has been put on masonry structures due to the large portion of the existing building stock that they encompass in many European areas, such as Italy, as well as due to their important historical and cultural value. In addition, a large number of existing masonry structures is prone to damage as a consequence of a wide number of possible actions, including environmental deterioration/aging, inadequate/old construction techniques, standards and materials, hazardous events. In this context, several retrofit/strengthening techniques have been developed for these buildings, often considering reversibility, compatibility and sustainability as beneficial requirements for the retrofit/strengthening process. Moreover, innovative techniques based on the use of technologies and materials compatible with physical and mechanical properties of

masonry are oftentimes required to economically improve the performance of such buildings. Among new strengthening strategies, the use of Fibre-Reinforced Polymer (FRP) strengthening technique provides a series of advantages, including high strength-to-weight ratios, corrosion and fatigue resistance, negligible influence on global structural mass, easy handling and installation, and low architectural impact. In terms of structural performance, the use of FRP can significantly enhance the tensile strength and global ductility of masonry panels. However, some drawbacks are also related to these materials, such as poor fire resistance, relatively high cost and environmental impacts.

Sustainability objectives are becoming essential driving principles for the development of innovative materials and technological solutions in the construction industry. Natural fibres represent an attractive alternative as reinforcing materials in structural applications due to both good mechanical properties and to the possibility to meet sustainability requirements [1-3]. Indeed, natural fibre reinforced composites are widely investigated trying to exploit their potential to reduce or eliminate some of the problems associated with the poor recyclability of glass and carbon fibres in conventional composites [4-6]. In addition, the production process of natural fibres consume globally less energy compared to typical fibres used in composite technology. However, the use of these fibres as reinforcement in composite materials remains a challenge mainly due the technological issue, like fibre orientation and compatibility with the matrix, and due to durability issues.

The present work deals with the in-plane structural behaviour of masonry panels strengthened with an innovative strengthening system obtained by using hemp fibres as reinforcing material in a composite grid.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experimental program consisted in diagonal compression tests carried out on 6 masonry panels. Masonry panels were built starting from yellow Neapolitan tuff bricks (370mm x 250mm x 115 mm of dimensions) and a pozzolan and lime based mortar having a thickness of approximately 12 mm in the panels. The resulting panels were ten courses high and one tuff block wide, having final dimensions of approximately 1200 mm × 1200 mm × 250 mm.

The 6 masonry panels were tested in three different configurations: *i*) two unreinforced panels used as control specimens (referred to as “P” series, Figure 4a); *ii*) two panels reinforced on both sides by means of one layer of hemp fiber composite (HFC) grid bonded with a pozzolan based mortar (referred to as HFC_PT reinforcing system, Figure 4b); *iii*) two panels reinforced on both sides by means of one layer of HFC grid bonded with a lime based mortar (referred to as HFC_MW reinforcing system, Figure 4c).

The strengthening systems were installed according the following procedure: preparation of the masonry substrate by means of a cleaning cycle with high-pressure water; pre-wetting until saturation of the substrate to prevent mortar drying out; application of a first layer of mortar (thickness of about 5-8 mm and 20mm for HFC_PT and HFC_MW series, respectively) onto both sides of the tuff panel; placement of one ply of HFC grid on each side of the panel; application of a second layer of mortar to complete the installation procedure (thickness of about 5-8 mm and 20mm for HFC_PT and HFC_MW series, respectively). The anchor system consists in two T and L connections placed on both panel sides, for HFC_PT and HFC_MW series, respectively. Specimen series, groups and labels are summarized in Table 1.

SERIES	Label	Mortar type	Reinforcing system	Anchor system
P	P1	-	-	-
	P2	-	-	-
HFC_PT	HFC_PT_1 HFC_PT_2	POZZOLAN based	HFC	T
HFC_MW	HFC_MW_1 HFC_MW_2	LIME based	HFC	L

Table 1: Masonry panel types.

2.1 Material properties

Mechanical properties of the tuff units and mortar used to build the masonry panels were determined by means of experimental tests. In particular, the flexural strength was obtained by means of three point bending tests, starting from prismatic specimens of 40mm x 40mm x 160mm dimension while the compressive strength was determined by using cubic samples of 40mm x 40mm x 40mm dimension. Flexural strength resulted in 1.5 ± 0.2 MPa and 1.5 ± 0.15 for tuff unit and mortar, respectively; whereas compressive strength resulted in 5.4 ± 0.4 MPa and 6.4 ± 0.3 , respectively.

The HFC grid used as innovative reinforcing system has a 20 mm x 20 mm bi-directional mesh and is made of hemp cords impregnated in a flexible epoxy resin. The usual way of producing hemp fabric composites consists in impregnating unidirectional hemp fibres within a given resin system. In the present study, before resin impregnation, each cord is obtained by twisting three single hemp 400 tex yarns, resulting in a final cord size of 3x400 tex (Figure 1). Then, the 3x400 tex hemp cords are manually weaved and placed over a 1.3 m x 1.3 m wooden framework in order to provide a the final 20 mm x 20 mm mesh configuration. The hemp grid is impregnated in a low viscosity (approximately 140 mPa·s) epoxy resin bath for a reasonable time long, in order to achieve a deeper resin penetration and complete impregnation of inner hemp fibres. In addition, the tensile mechanical performance of the single impregnated hemp cord is optimized by varying the content of resin within the composite. The final resin content of each impregnated cord was approximately 60% in volume, leading to a tensile strength of about 300 N and a grid tensile resistance of approximately 20 kN/m.

Figure 1: (a) Single hemp cord made of 3x400 tex hemp yarns and (b) impregnated HFC grid.

Two different mortars were used to bond the HFC external reinforcement onto the masonry panels. A pozzolan based mortar (used in the HFC_PT series) was obtained by mixing hydraulic lime and sand (ratio 1:3) and by adding short glass fibers (about 10% of the total weight) mixed with latex and water (ratio 1:2). The mechanical properties of this matrix type after 28 days of curing were determined by means of 8 tests on prismatic specimens 40mm x 40mm x 160mm: flexural strength of 8.0 MPa; compressive strength of 16.1 MPa; and tensile strength 6.0 MPa. The final thickness of the mortar applied on each side of the panel was 15 mm. A lime based mortar (used in the HFC_MW series) was obtained by mixing natural hydraulic lime, reactive inorganic compounds and natural sand. The mechanical properties of this matrix type after 28 days of curing were determined by means of 3 tests on prismatic specimens 40mm x 40mm x 160mm: flexural strength of 6.0 MPa; compressive strength of 14.2 MPa. The final thickness of the mortar applied on each side of the panel was 40 mm.

2.2 Test Setup

The 6 panels were tested in a new steel frame outdoor set-up that allows the application of the compression load along one diagonal (Figure 2). The maximum load capacity of the system is 500 kN both in tension and in compression with a total stroke equals ± 75 mm.

To avoid a premature splitting failure of the panel edges, two steel loading shoes were used to apply the machine load to the specimen according to the ASTM E 519-02. The spaces between the specimen and steel loading shoes were filled with fast setting and shrinkage free mortar. To avoid friction and constrain to the deformation of the masonry panel, the spaces between the specimen and the support was filled of several layer of very low density foam material. Four linear displacement variable transducers (LVDTs) over a gauge length of 400 mm were used to monitor in-plane displacements. In particular, two LVDTs were placed on each panel side along the diagonals to record the shortening and elongation of vertical and horizontal diagonals, respectively.

Figure 2: Geometrical details of the experimental set up for diagonal compression tests.

The tests were carried out under displacement control, in order to record the panels post-peak response; the displacement rate was 0.02 mm/sec for all tests. Tests were stopped when the reduction in compressive load was about 50% with respect to the peak value. The results of the diagonal compressive tests are handled according to the ASTM E 519-02. In detail, the shear stress τ , shear strain γ and modulus of rigidity G are obtained as follows (equations 1-2-3, respectively):

$$\tau = \frac{0.707P}{A_n} \quad (1)$$

where:

τ is the shear stress on net area A_n ,

P is the applied load,

A_n is the net area of the specimen calculated as: $A_n = \left(\frac{W + h}{2} \right) tn$, being w the width, h the height, t

the total thickness of the specimen, and n the percent of the gross area of the unit that is solid (assumed as 1). The average vertical and horizontal strains, ϵ_v and ϵ_h , are computed as the average displacement on the two sides over the gauge length (400 mm) along the compressive and tensile diagonals, respectively.

$$\gamma = \frac{\Delta V + \Delta H}{g} \quad (2)$$

where:

γ is the shearing strain,

ΔV is the vertical shortening,

ΔH is the horizontal extension,

g is the vertical gage length.

$$G = \frac{\tau}{\gamma} \quad (3)$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental τ - γ strain relationships, computed according equations 1-2, are showed in Figure 3 for the control panels and the two strengthened ones. The main experimental outcomes are summarized in Table 2. Unreinforced tuff panels P1 and P2 are characterized by a very similar behavior that is relatively linear up to the maximum shear stress (that is recorded in correspondence to the peak load, V_{max}), $\tau_{max} = 0.296$ MPa, and $\tau_{max} = 0.237$ MPa for specimen for P1 and P2, respectively. The observed post-peak response was very limited due to the sudden shear failure of both unreinforced panels. Panels of HFC_PT series exhibited a nearly linear behavior up to the peak shear stress which reached an average value of 0.50 MPa, corresponding to approximately two times higher than the average maximum shear stress achieved on the unreinforced panels. The post peak response was characterized by an almost linear softening behavior (with a lower slope than the initial one) up to the ultimate failure reached at $\gamma \approx 2.5\%$ of shear strain. In this case, the strengthening behavior allowed large shear strain during post peak response, increasing the overall ductility of the panel (see $\mu = \gamma_u / \gamma_{max}$) in Table 2). This is plausibly due to the glass fibers embedded in the pozzolan based matrix that allows a better distribution of tensile loads in the matrix after that matrix cracking occurs.

The other two panels of HFC_MW series reached higher shear strength values than the HFC_PT system. In particular, the maximum shear strength τ_{max} ranged between 0.73 and 0.77 MPa, corresponding to a further increase of about 50% than the HFC_PT system and approximately three times higher than the unreinforced masonry panels. However, HFC_MW panels were characterized by a shorter post peak response than HFC_PT specimens, that led to an ultimate failure at approximately $\gamma \approx 1.0\%$ of shear strain.

From τ - γ curves, the modulus of rigidity G was computed according to equation 3; it is calculated as the secant modulus between the origin and the stress equal 30% of the peak shear stress (see Table 2). The experimental results in terms of modulus of rigidity showed that the stiffness of the panels was affected by the two different matrices used to bond the HFC grid. In particular, the pozzolan based matrix system slightly increased the overall panels stiffness (i.e. from ≈ 500 MPa to ≈ 600 MPa). The stiffness increase was much more relevant in the case of HFC_MW series that where characterized by a modulus of rigidity around three times higher than control panels.

Specimen	τ_{max} [MPa]	$\tau_u (0.8 \cdot \tau_{max})$ [MPa]	ν [-]	γ_{max} [%]	γ_u [%]	G [MPa]	$\mu (\gamma_u / \gamma_{max})$ [-]
P1	0.296	-	0.483	0.081	-	529	-
P2	0.237	0.190	0.434	0.105	0.108	424	1.04
HFC_PT_1	0.454	0.363	0.649	0.281	1.599	572	5.68
HFC_PT_2	0.540	0.432	0.693	0.178	0.807	629	4.52
HFC_MW_1	0.766	-	0.642	0.587	-	1212	-
HFC_MW_2	0.737	0.590	0.240	0.063	0.448	1829	7.13

Table 2: Experimental test outcomes.

Figure 3: τ - γ curves of tested panels.

All strengthened panels exhibited a different crack pattern and failure mode if compared to control ones. In particular, on control specimens P1 and P2, the shear failure was due to a wide pseudo-vertical crack, mainly developing along the mortar joints (see Figure 4a'-b'-c'). On the contrary, strengthened panels were characterized by a more uniform crack pattern that developed uniformly along the loading direction. Some cracks, less wide than those observed on control specimens, were attained also away from the loading direction only in the case of HFC_PT series. The crack size was significantly larger in case of HFC_MW panels, demonstrating a more brittle behavior of the lime based mortar (also inferable in Figure 4-c') if compared to the HFC_PT series. Indeed, the use of pozzolan based mortar combined with short fibers induced less wide cracks. The HFC grid brakeage was almost brittle and was observed along the crack direction in all tested strengthened panels.

The structural behavior observed in this study can be effectively compared with other commercial/available strengthening systems applied to masonry structures. For instance, in the work by Balsamo et al. [7], tuff masonry panels were tested under compression diagonal tests and reinforced with pre-cured alkali-resistant basalt or glass FRP bonded with a cement based mortar or pre-mixed high ductility hydraulic lime and pozzolan based mortar, i.e. with a very similar configuration with respect to the present testing campaign. From those results, it can be observed that the use of the above mentioned strengthening systems led to maximum shear strength values of around 0.50-0.60 MPa with respect to approximately 0.15 MPa of unreinforced ones. These results demonstrate that the proposed system can be successfully used as external reinforcing system for masonry structures.

a)

a')

b)

b')

Figure 4: (a-a') Undamaged configuration and failure modes: control specimen; (b-b') HFC_PT_1 specimen; (c-c') HFC_MW_2 specimen.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the in-plane response of reinforced tuff masonry panels has been investigated. The reinforcing system consisted of an innovative hemp fibre composite bi-directional grid, externally bonded to the panels by means of two different mortars, i.e. a pozzolan based and a lime based mortar. The strengthening system was conceived to pursue sustainable goals in construction industry and, specifically, to effectively employ natural fiber in structural retrofit/rehabilitation activities.

The proper impregnation of the twisted hemp yarns through a flexible epoxy resin allowed the exploitation of the good tensile properties of hemp fibres. Indeed, the experimental outcomes, in terms of diagonal compression behaviour, showed enhanced mechanical properties in all the investigated reinforced panels. In particular, the maximum shear strength was increased by a factor 2 and 3 in the case of HFC_PT and HFC_MW series, respectively.

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